

Baby Boom

Baby Boom maternity hospital implements a smart information system for automation and monitoring of newborn care. The system will be installed on a central computer with a dedicated database, accessible through terminals in various rooms (reception, treatment units, newborn rooms). Monitor displays that will be located in the newborn department will provide real-time alerts on the condition of the babies.

For each staff member, the system will store the employee number, name, and position. Complete employee details are maintained in the HR system and transferred from time to time through a dedicated interface (API).

When a baby is born, the nurse performs initial registration, including: birth date, weight, height, mother's ID number, mother's full name, and birth date. For mothers who do not exist in the system, the nurse will enter the mother's details (ID number, full name, birth date, and phone number). The nurse will indicate whether the baby is breastfed, receives formula, or a combination of both. During registration, the nurse will assign smart bracelets to the baby and the mother and will connect them in the system. Since babies receive ID numbers only upon release, the system generates unique bracelet numbers for babies identification. The mother's bracelet number is her ID number.

The nurse will assign for each baby a smart crib with a unique number that communicates with the bracelet through the system. Smart cribs include built-in components (a breathing sensor, a scale) and a small computer with a touch screen connected to the system. Upon assignment, the system calibrates the crib. If the calibration fails, another crib should be assigned. The initial registration cannot be completed without a successful crib assignment. In successful calibration, the calibration timestamp will be saved in the system.

Baby Examination: The staff can perform a range of examinations. For each examination type, various metrics are defined, e.g., haemoglobin exam includes WBC, RBC, etc.. For each metric, the following information is saved: name, upper boundary, lower boundary, and measurement unit. Examination results are stored along with the time when the sample was taken and the time when the result was entered (which may vary for different metrics within the same examination). The system will check the results against the boundaries defined in the system and display alerts on the newborn room screen for deviations from the ranges. The staff can generate an "abnormal examination report" for specific date ranges showing metrics outside boundaries. Examination types, metrics and boundaries are updated through the interface to the Ministry of Health system HC. A staff member can generate an abnormal examination report for a specific baby within a selected date range. The report will include, for that baby, the details of examinations in which abnormal metric values were found. For each such examination, the following will be displayed: the examination date, the name of the examination type, the name of the abnormal metric, and the recorded result.

Routine Actions: Feeding and diaper changing are performed by either the mother or a staff member. The mother can document feeding or diaper change using a touchscreen attached to the baby's crib. If the action is performed by staff, their details will be recorded.

- **Feeding:** Every feeding event must be recorded by the mother or staff. The feeding type (breastfeeding/amount of formula) must be entered, and the system will save the timestamp.
- **Diaper Change:** Every diaper change must be documented by the mother or staff. The system requires input on stool presence and diaper wetness level (a number between 1–5). The system will check and alert for abnormal wetness levels (higher or lower by more than Y% from dryness/wetness thresholds defined by the management and stored in the system).

- **Weighing:** The crib will weigh the baby three times a day. Once the weight data is received, the system will check and alert if the baby loses more than X% of his weight within 24 hours (X will be defined by the management and saved in the system).

Upon release, the nurse disconnects the baby's and mother's bracelet assignments from the crib.